

AI Should Augment Human Intelligence, Not Replace It: A Dentist Perspective

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence is the ability of machines to perform task that typically require human intelligence. It has various subdivisions such as machine learning and deep learning. Artificial intelligence is thought to replace humans in a number of domains

and aspects as it is evolving rapidly . The fields of medicine and dentistry are also anticipating it. AI is now believed to provide diagnosis, treatment planning, and prognosis, raising the possibility that it could take the role of dentists in a number of crucial procedures. This essay will briefly go over some of the ways artificial intelligence (AI) can be used in dentistry, emphasizing that AI should be used in addition to human intellect (dentists) rather than as a replacement.

Key words : Artificial intelligence, AI, AI in Dentistry.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence has come a long way from its inception in 1951, when Christopher Strachey wrote the first program. In 1956 the word "artificial intelligence" was used for the first time by John McCarthy at the Dartmouth Conference. This marked the start of the present era of artificial intelligence. AI research concentrated on rule-based and expert systems during the 1960s and 1970s, while in 1980s and 1990s the main focus was machine learning and neural networks that programmed computers to learn and work accordingly from data and progressively become more adept at what they were doing [1].

AI is rapidly developing and is being used for diagnosis, treatment and prognosis . It can serve as an augmentation tool by dentists to help them integrating patient data , fostering better professional connections and also assist them in treatment [2]. However, since AI can only help with treatments that are programmed into it and information that is put into its system, a dentist cannot fully rely on it. There is no doubt that these technologies have the potential to improve dentistry, but they also pose legal dangers and ethical difficulties [3]. As a result, this article will provide

insight into how artificial intelligence is not replacing human intelligence (dentist), but rather complementing it.

Understanding AI?

Artificial intelligence is the science of developing technology, creating software, and manufacturing machines that have human-like intellect and can perform tasks for us. To put it briefly, artificial intelligence (AI) is a term developed in the 1950s used to describe machines that mimic human intellect [4]. As an example, the T-800 in the film Terminator represents an AI [5].

Machine Learning (ML) And Deep Learning (DL)

One subfield of artificial intelligence is machine learning, which includes deep learning as its subfield. (fig. 1). To understand machine learning, let's take an example of you purchasing clothes online in medium size, and the next time you view certain clothing items, it will display the size recommended for you as of medium in various outfits and labels. As the system learns from the information you previously provided while ordering on the same application, this is exactly what machine learning is. Additionally, if you search for an item on any shopping application, several social media networks will provide referrals of things from the same category from several purchasing sites. That is what the software program learns from the information you provide to it. In summary, in machine learning the system will learn and work based on its past experience.

Figure 1- AI and its subfields

Again, this time, before searching for a clothing piece, you first furnish the application with comprehensive details about your sizes. Now it will provide you with an accurate size fit recommendation based on the data you provided. This recommendation will be precise regardless of the clothing brand and style, as the application will assimilate information from both your input and from the brands and styles to provide you with an accurate size and fit recommendation. This is what deep learning is. To conclude, the methods by which each algorithm learns and the quantity and type of data that they need vary for ML and DL. AI in machine learning will adjust on its own with little assistance from humans, whereas more data points are needed for a deep learning model to increase accuracy.

Humans And AI

Without people AI cannot exist. Humans create and build AI, alter and use it. Artificial intelligence can work more quickly than human and, as contrast to humans,

it never physically tires. AI-based devices and software are quicker, more precise, more consistently logical, but they lack emotional intelligence, cultural sensitivity, or intuition. And these characteristics are exactly what characterise human and give us our efficacy. Human potential is more diverse. People can imagine, anticipate, feel, and judge changing events, but AI skills are limited to the facts supplied. In contrast to artificial intelligence, which is dependent on a constant supply of information from external sources, human skills are distinct .[6]

AI And Dentistry

AI is increasingly being used in the medical area, including significant advancements in dentistry [7]. Classifiers and predictive AI algorithms can anticipate the long-term effects of dental ailments by examining relationships among clinical signs and symptom, related variables and patient data. They also help identify risk factors. AI can schedule a list of patients with their current requirements as well as medical details that can make it possible to anticipate medication-related problems unique to a given patient. It could also aid in staging, diagnosis as well as outcome forecasting [8]. Radiomic characteristics such as shape, size, connection between voxels and pixels, gray-level occurrence matrix, textures created out of filtered photos and intricate fractal elements are interpretable from 2D or 3D images. These radiographic features can help diagnose bone disorders as well as cancer. They anticipate treatment outcomes of oncotherapy, and estimate functional parameters [9-28]. Combining imaging characteristics with clinical data and genetic information can increase diagnosis and prediction accuracy. [11] Potential for automatic segmentation of head and neck structures could reduce errors and save time for radiologists. Manual segmentation takes a lot of time and requires an operator. Developments in the

automated technique could enhance radiomic analysis, radiation therapy planning, and virtual surgical planning [7].

Based on the patient's parameters, a multi layer perceptron neural network accurately predicted the durability and tooth mobility of resin composite restorations [29]. As stated by Yamaguchi et al. CNNs were successful in properly forecasting chance of CAD/CAM resin composite crown de-bonding. In the future, regenerative dental techniques could be evaluated in a simulated inflammatory micro-environment using a prediction model that combines artificial neural networks. Excellent sensitivity in classifying cytology images obtained from a telemedicine platform as malignant (93%) or high-grade potential malignant (73%) lesions [30].

In a RCT carried out by Rajan RS, et al (2024) Kumar HK, Sekhar A, Nadakkavukaran D, Feroz SM, Gangadharappa P (2024) where they evaluated the prediction of success on dental implants in two groups that were AI group and traditional method group by using preoperative CBCT images. 150 patients in need of dental implants were split into two groups at random for this RCT. While the traditional assessment group depended on conventional procedures and physician skill, the AI-assisted group assessed implant success likelihood based on CBCT images using a machine learning model built on historical data. The AI model considered important factors such anatomical characteristics, bone density, and bone quality. Following the study's conclusion, 92% of implants in the AI-assisted group effectively integrated into the bone, compared to 78% in the traditional evaluation group. This represents a considerable increase in implant success rates [31]

Dentists, AI and Dentistry

Figure 2 - Dental professionals' and AI's roles in patient care

Discussion

It's critical to recognize the unique roles that AI technology plays in comparison to those that can only be filled by humans as AI tools and technologies become more integrated into dentistry.

AI is a great help in storing all the patient's personal data, medical history, dental history, and history of habits and allergies. When a patient visits the dental clinician, AI can help by displaying all this information to the dentist, cutting down on time and minimizing errors in taking history, which can happen if the patient is hiding something or is unable to recall everything. All this data is input into the AI by humans themselves. The availability of data determines how far deep learning-based methods can be used. Data in medicine, particularly dentistry, is not readily available due to data protection concerns. Additionally, certain obstacles, such as comparatively smaller size and lack of structure, make applications of artificial intelligence techniques difficult [32].

AI comprises of algorithms that break down input photos into fundamental characteristics like edges, gradients, shapes, signal strength, wavelengths, and textures that can be utilized to categorize or interpret the image. Accurate diagnosis, prognosis, and prediction may be improved by clinical decision-making through the connection of AI-generated data with clinical and biological outcomes. Within this context, radiography has undergone a transformation from an arbitrary art of perception to an objective scientific discipline. As a result, deep neural network-based automatic techniques have been explored for several uses, including classification, picture production, enhancement, lesion detection, segmentation, registration, retrieval, and guided therapy [7]. Specialized knowledge from healthcare practitioners is required for the annotation of medical data. Additionally, the process of data labeling is

expensive and demands a sufficient labour. Deep-learning algorithms are unable to produce reliable interpretations and predictions in the absence of increasing flow of accurately labelled data. Limited generalizability of deep learning models is caused by varying imaging properties. To aid in the creation of more effective modelling techniques, the underlying potential generalizability deficiencies need to be clarified. Achieving high sensitivity and specificity may not always be possible for AI models because of variations in anatomical architecture and image quality. Dental picture interpretation is challenging due to the overlapping features and artifacts. To guarantee precise and trustworthy interpretation of dental pictures, AI models should be able to overcome these obstacles [32].

Despite all of the advances in medical knowledge, effective disease detection is still viewed as challenging globally. This is because different diseases have diverse causes and symptoms, making it difficult to create early diagnostic techniques. AI has the power to revolutionise healthcare in a number of ways, including diagnosis. One area of artificial intelligence that uses data as an input resource is machine learning. The volume and quality of the input data have a major impact on machine learning accuracy, which can assist reduce the complexity and challenges associated with diagnosis. In conclusion, machine learning (ML) has the potential to facilitate timely and cost-effective task automation, workflow management, and decision-making. Additionally, layers utilizing Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and data mining are introduced by deep learning to identify patterns in data. When analyzing huge datasets linked to illness detection, these are quite helpful in identifying significant trends. These tools are particularly helpful for diagnosing, predicting, or classifying illnesses in healthcare systems [1].

Expertise gained via in-depth study and real-world experience is necessary to give precise diagnosis and treatment recommendations. The complex decision-making that seasoned clinicians are capable of may not be entirely replicated by AI. Dental conditions can present in a variety of ways. These variations could be in terms of size, shape, or appearance. Artificial intelligence systems need to be able to take these disparities into account in order to detect and classify different ailments in an efficient manner. One of the main challenges in automated dental disease diagnosis is bridging the gap between human competence and AI capabilities [32].

In addition, many dental offices have digital patient records; the doctor may be able to diagnose and arrange a course of therapy using these pre-existing images. It can also be used to monitor progress and adherence to treatment. Images captured with a mobile might be useful while gathering information for a clinical condition assessment through online platforms or remote conversations. It is anticipated that artefact reduction, low-dose imaging, automated analysis of 2D and 3D image datasets to identify artifacts and technical errors, and reduced radiation exposure will lead to a significant improvement in image quality and quality analysis. Therefore, the advantages of consistency, repeatability, cost savings, time savings, and increased intelligence make AI potentially useful. The doctor is in charge of each patient and the way the data is used. Regardless of whether AI is used in an unsupervised or supervised setting, it is not accountable. Determining legal obligation creates an ethical quandary [32].

Conclusion

Artificial intelligence is very useful in health care. AI systems can continuously analyse variables like disease frequency, population demographics, and geographic dispersion. This can identify patients who are more likely to develop particular illnesses, which can aid in therapy or prevention . AI can help clinicians by enhancing the precision of diagnosis, improving judgement and predicting the course of treatment, all of which can help medical professionals give patients the best possible treatment. This is an invaluable advantage as it might potentially save many lives .

It is critical to recognize that, despite these developments, artificial intelligence cannot replace the priceless contribution of human knowledge and experience. The limitations and difficulties covered in this article highlight the necessity of human experience in resolving difficult diagnostic situations and choosing the best course of action. Although AI can support and enhance doctors' abilities, it is unable to completely replace the sophisticated decision-making process that seasoned professionals are capable of. Consequently, rather than taking the place of human experts in dentistry, the application of AI should be viewed as an additional tool that improves clinical practice. To further secure patient trust and safeguard sensitive information, ethical issues such data accessibility, openness, and privacy must be carefully handled .

Dentists' knowledge is necessary for more complex understanding since robots incapable of providing clinical intuition, intangible perception, or empathy—all of which are necessary for professionalism and individualized healthcare . It is only partially able to make complex judgments in a therapeutic situation, and it is unable to create associations. The most exciting part of human-to-human conversation cannot

be translated into computer language directly. The growth of AI and dental education ought to go hand in hand .

References

1. Alowais SA, Alghamdi SS, Alsuhebany N, Alqahtani T, Alshaya AI, Almohareb SN, Aldairem A, Alrashed M, Bin Saleh K, Badreldin HA, Al Yami MS. Revolutionizing healthcare: the role of artificial intelligence in clinical practice. BMC medical education. 2023 Sep 22;23(1):689.
2. Han K, Cao P, Wang Y, Xie F, Ma J, Yu M, Wang J, Xu Y, Zhang Y, Wan J. A review of approaches for Predicting Drug-Drug interactions based on machine learning. Front Pharmacol. 2022;12:814858.
3. Kumar PR, Ravindranath KV, Srilatha V, Alobaoid MA, Kulkarni MM, Mathew T, Tiwari HD. Analysis of advances in research trends in robotic and digital dentistry: An original research. Journal of Pharmacy and Bioallied Sciences. 2022 Jul 1;14(Suppl 1):S185-7
4. What is artificial intelligence (AI)? Everything you need to know [Nicole Laskowski](#), Senior News Director [Linda Tucci](#), Industry Editor -- CIO/IT Strategy
5. Feng QJ, Harte M, Carey B, Alqarni A, Monteiro L, Diniz-Freitas M, Fricain JC, Lodi G, Brailo V, Andreoletti M, Albuquerque R. The risks of artificial intelligence: A narrative review and ethical reflection from an Oral Medicine group. Oral diseases. 2024.
6. De Cremer D, Kasparov G. AI should augment human intelligence, not replace it. Harvard Business Review. 2021 Mar 18;18(1).

7. Leite AF, Vasconcelos KD, Willems H, Jacobs R. Radiomics and machine learning in oral healthcare. *PROTEOMICS–Clinical Applications*. 2020 May;14(3):1900040.
8. Jimma BL: Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Telematics and Informatics Reports*. 2023; 9: 100041
9. M. McBee, O. Awan, A. Colucci, C. Ghobadi, N. Kadom, A. Kansagra, S. Tridandapani, W. Auffermann, *Acad. Radiol.* 2018, 25, 1472.
10. B. Erickson, P. Korfiatis, Z. Akkus, T. Kline, K. Philbrick, J. Digit. Imaging. 2017, 30, 400.
11. H., Slavkin, J. *Public Health Dent*. 2018 in press, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jphd.12296>.
12. J. Thrall, X. Li, Q. Li, C. Cruz, S. Do, K. Dreyer, J. Brink, *J. Am. Coll. Radiol.* 2018,15, 504. [22] T. Litman, *APMIS* 2019, 127, 386.
13. E. Shortliffe, M. Sepúlveda, *JAMA* 2018, 320, 2199
14. K. van Leeuwen, H. Sun, M. Tabaeizadeh, A. Struck, M. van Putten, M. Westover, *Clin. Neurophysiol.* 2018, 130, 77.
15. Y. Kim, J. Lee, I. Yu, H. Song, I. Baek, J. Seong, H. Jeong, B. Kim, H. Nam, J. Chung, O. Bang, G. Kim, W. Seo, *Stroke* 2019, 50, 1444.
16. F. PaN, P. He, F. Chen, J. Zhang, H. Wang, D. Zheng, *Int. J. Med. Inform.* 2019, 128, 71.
17. C. Kruse, *Curr. Osteoporosis Rep.* 2018, 16, 320.
18. U. Ferizi, S. Honig, G. Chang, *Curr. Opin. Rheumatol.* 2019, 31, 368.
19. N. T. Duc, S. Ryu, M. N. I Qureshi, M. Choi, K. H Lee, B. Lee, *Neuroinformatics*. 2019 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12021-019-09419-w>

20. Z. Tang, K. V. Chuang, C. DeCarli, L. W. Jin, L. Beckett, M. J. Keiser, B. N. Dugger, *Nat. Commun.* 2019, 10, 2173.
21. Y. Fujinami-Yokokawa, N. Pontikos, L. Yang, K. Tsunoda, T. Yoshitake, T. Iwata, H. Miyata, K. Fujinami, *J. Ophthalmol.* 2019, 2019, 1691064.
22. N. Lüneburg, N. Reiss, C. Feldmann, P. van der Meulen, M. van de Steeg, T. Schmidt, R. Wendl, S. Jansen, *Stud. Health Technol. Inform.* 2019, 260, 192.
23. A. Khalighifar, E. Komp, J. Ramsey, R. Gurgel-Gonçalves, A. Peterson, *J. Med. Entomol.* 2019, 56,1404. in press.
24. D. Ardila, A. Kiraly, C. Bharadwaj, B. Choi, J. Reicher, L. Peng, D. Tse, M. Etemadi, W. Ye, G. Corrado, D. Naidich, S. Shetty, *Nat. Med.* 2019, 25, 954.
25. C. Wang, C. Hamm, L. Savic, M. Ferrante, I. Schobert, T. Schlachter, M. Lin, J. Weinreb, J. Duncan, J. Chapiro, B. Letzen, *Eur. Radiol.* 2019, 29, 3348.
26. D. Truhn, S. Schradling, C. Haarburger, H. Schneider, D. Merhof, C. Kuhl, *Radiology.* 2019, 290, 290.
27. P. Lambin, R. Leijenaar, T. Deist, J. Peerlings, E. de Jong, J. van Timmeren, S. Sanduleanu, R. Larue, A. Even, A. Jochems, Y. van Wijk, H. Woodruff, J. van Soest, T. Lustberg, E. Roelofs, W. van Elmpt, A. Dekker, F. Mottaghy, J. Wildberger, S. Walsh, *Nat. Rev. Clin. Oncol.* 2017, 14, 749
28. Yamaguchi S, Lee C, Karaer O, et al.: Predicting the Debonding of CAD/CAM Composite Resin Crowns with AI. *J. Dent. Res.* 2019 Oct; 98(11): 1234–1238. Epub 2019 Aug 3
29. Shan T, Tay FR, Gu L: Application of Artificial Intelligence in Dentistry. *J. Dent. Res.* 2021; 100(3): 232–244

30. Rajan RS, Kumar HK, Sekhar A, Nadakkavukaran D, Feroz SM, Gangadharappa P. Evaluating the Role of AI in Predicting the Success of Dental Implants Based on Preoperative CBCT Images: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Journal of Pharmacy and Bioallied Sciences*. 2024 Feb 1;16(Suppl 1):S889-91.
31. Shafi I, Fatima A, Afzal H, Díez ID, Lipari V, Breñosa J, Ashraf I. A comprehensive review of recent advances in artificial intelligence for dentistry E-health. *Diagnostics*. 2023 Jun 28;13(13):2196.
32. Zhang H, Chen Y, Li F. Predicting Anticancer Drug Response with Deep Learning constrained by signaling pathways. *Front Bioinform*. 2021;1:639349.